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The role of magnetic resonance tomography in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant ovarian neoplasms

Khaydarova G. B.

Suleymanova Ch.Sh.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Objective

Learning the role of magnetic resonance tomography in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant ovarian neoplasms and comparing it with other methods.

Material and methods

There have been studied 20 cases of ovarian tumors among 30-60-year-old women at the Republican Specialized Scientific Applied Oncology Center and the Tashkent City Oncology Dispensary in 2020-2021 to conduct the research. It was used 1.5 T Philips magnetic resonance tomography device to image the pelvis and abdomen in patients and were used sonographic images obtained by the Sonoscape ultrasound device for the purpose of comparison.

Results

There were defined 8 cases of a benign ovarian tumor (40%), 11 cases of a malignant ovarian tumor (55%) and 1 case of an intermediate condition (5%) among the studied patients.

There were revealed solid-cystic formations of uncertain polygonal shape, ascites,

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lymphadenopathy in the regional lymph nodes and were detected a certain amount of fluid in the pelvic cavity in the ovarian malignant tumor.

The specificity of ultrasound was 86% and the sensitivity was 92% in researching ovarian tumors. And specificity of MRI examination was performed 88% and sensitivity was 95%.

There were identified 22% of cases with a solid component, 31% with a solid-cystic component, and 47% with a cystic component during the study of 11 malignant tumor diseases in the researching of ovarian tumors.

Conclusion

Magnetic resonance tomography examination method is one of the main methods in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant tumors of the ovary.

It was identified many cases with a cystic component (majority 47%) with this method of diagnosis.

It can be concluded taking into account cases with a cystic component are accurately depicted in the MRI examination, that this method is important for correct diagnosis despite the fact that it is expensive and time-consuming.

